

CONSERVATION OF ENERGY AND MOMENTUM IN THE GENERATION OF ELECTRON AND POSITRON FROM THE VACUUM ACCORDING TO THE "ULTIMATE EQUILIBRIUM" MATHEMATICAL MODEL

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Abstract

This article describes the conservation of energy in special relativity in the generation of the electron-positron pair from the vacuum, according to the "ultimate equilibrium" mathematical model (Ref. 1). The incident waves on the virtual bosons of space-time excite the bosons leading to the appearance of virtual particles. At the conditions of ultimate equilibrium the passage from virtual particles to real particles takes place.

Introduction

The generation of pairs from the vacuum is a phenomenon that occurs both in accelerators and spontaneously. Starting from the initial, physically contemplable situation of a region of space-time made by virtual bosons (we will call them "immaterial atom"- "i.a."), adjacent but with alternately opposite spins, $s=+1\hbar$ and $s=-1\hbar$, each made up of two virtual elementary electric charges e^+ and e^- (note A) whose effect on space-time is comparable to that of two rotating elementary charges, perfectly overlapped, with the same direction of rotation and therefore with zero fields, the equation that describes the situation in which these virtual particles present in the vacuum, excited by electromagnetic waves incident in opposite directions, become real ("ultimate equilibrium") has been determined (Ref.1). The formula is valid exclusively in this transition situation. The purpose of this article is to demonstrate that this model respects the conservation of energy in special relativity.

Methods

The space-time region under examination, made up of a grid of bosons with zero fields, can be considered homogeneous and isotropic and, characterized by the same values of electrical permittivity ϵ_0 and magnetic permeability μ_0 as the physical vacuum, equals its behaviour.

Based on the values of the incident waves on these bosons we distinguish three situations.

1. VIRTUAL AND ATTRACTIVE PHASE/BOSONIC PHYSICS

In this phase the two overlapped electric charges (virtual particles, i.a.) are partially separated along the spin direction from the magnetic component of the incident waves, which have an insufficient value to reach the "ultimate equilibrium" condition (Ref.1) . Both their electric charge and their magnetic dipoles exert an attractive force to restore the initial condition of an unperturbed boson. The value of the electric and magnetic attractive forces depends on the portions of electric charge that are no longer overlapped and are separating, a phenomenon that we will define as "unmasking". This value cannot be determined, as the charge distribution is not known and the portion of charges that unmask, based on the magnitude of the incident wave, is not known. Once the wave has passed, the attractive forces between the two electric charges restore the initial condition and the presence of the virtual particles is no longer perceived. In the unperturbed condition the electric and magnetic forces between the two virtual charges, now perfectly overlapped, have a zero value. In reality this condition does not occur due to the background radiation, but represents the unperturbed equilibrium condition towards which these virtual bosons would tend.

Below is the energy balance in the virtual phase.

$$E_1 = E_{m\text{virt}} + W_{\text{virt}} \quad (1)$$

where

$E_1 = h\omega_1$ is the incident energy ($E_1 < E_*$ = ultimate equilibrium energy)

$E_{m\text{virt}}$ is the amount of energy relative to the portions of virtual charge that are separating due to the effect of incident waves (unmasking)

c = light speed

W_{virt} = work done by the incident waves to separate the virtual charges.

2. ULTIMATE EQUILIBRIUM CONDITION

In this situation, shown in Figure 1, the incident waves have such a value that they have separated the two virtual charges to the point where the equal magnetic poles of their magnetic dipoles overlap (in the initial condition of not perturbed equilibrium the poles of the respective magnetic dipoles are overlapped but of opposite sign). The distance between the centres of the two electric fields that are separating and distinguishing coincides with the radius of the electron's or positron's electric field

itself R_{e1} (Ref.1). The magnetic force ceases completely and only the electric force remains (Ref.1).

The energy balance can be described by:

$$E_* = 2h\omega_* = 2 * \frac{K_o Q_o^2}{c} * \omega_* + W_{*virt} \quad (2)$$

in which

$E_* = 2h\omega_*$ is the energy of the incident waves at the frequency of last equilibrium
 $\omega_* = 1,0638E+23$ 1/s

W_{*virt} is the work done by the incident waves to separate the virtual charges up to the ultimate equilibrium distance

$E_m = 2 * \frac{K_o Q_o^2}{c} * \omega_*$ corresponds to the amount of energy of the virtual charges that will become real mass (Ref.1). The energy is that of the electric charges, whose energy state is conditioned by the frequency of the wave that excites them. Doing the calculations for the single particle, for which $|Q_o| = 1,6022E-19$ C is the electron's or positron's electric charge, we get in fact (note B)

$$E_m = \frac{K_o Q_o^2}{c} * \omega_* = 0,511 \text{MeV} \quad (3)$$

As concluded in the article (Ref.1), colliding waves at the ultimate equilibrium frequency leads to conditions that promote the generation of pairs. **The energy at the ultimate equilibrium frequency is $E_* = 2h\omega_* = 880 \text{MeV}$. From numerous laboratory reports it emerges that production peaks can be detected around 880MeV.** Instead to a "hadronic contamination"¹, according to our opinion and still under study, this concentration² could be due to the mechanism we described.

Energy fluctuations, in the general real case, will condition the behavior starting from the ultimate equilibrium situation, which is an unstable equilibrium. Three possibilities are identified.

- a. The electric charges immediately return to the initial position discussed above.
- b. The charges remain connected for a short period and then return to their initial condition. During this period they manifest a state of oscillation, known as the

¹ R. Preghenella for the ALICE Collaboration, *Light-flavour identified charged-hadron production in pp and Pb–Pb collisions at the LHC*, *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* 455 (2013) 01200

² *Measurement of electrons from hadron decays with charm and beauty in Pb-Pb collisions at LHC with ALICE*, Faggini M. Thesis Department of Physics and Astronomy "Galileo Galilei" of Padova.

Zitterbewegung phenomenon. A possible physical explanation is that, as we can see in the graph shown in Figure 1 (Ref.1),

Figure 1

Configuration of "ultimate equilibrium" at the moment of generation and separation of the electron e^- and the positron e^+ .

The distance φ between the centres of the two electric fields coincides with the radius $r=R_{el}=2,8180E-15m$ of the electric field of the real particle (Ref.1)

at the condition of "ultimate equilibrium", in which the coincident magnetic poles do not exchange force, the electric fields of the two electric charges are assuming the spherical configuration with the known radius of the electron (Ref. 1). However, a small portion of the electric field is still overlapped. The partial overlap of the two electric fields, combined with even minimal or imperceptible energy fluctuations in space-time, conditions the repulsive action between the poles in a mathematically unpredictable way when an infinitesimal shift from the ultimate equilibrium condition occurs.

- c. If from this position we do not return to the virtual condition, then the two electric fields move apart, becoming the electric fields of the real particles, as described below.

3. REAL AND REPULSIVE PHASE/FERMIONIC PHYSICS

In this phase the magnetic dipoles of the two charges become unbalanced in such a direction that their repulsion further distances the two electric fields. As a consequence, the electric charges move away from each other and become real fermions (Ref.1) (note C). According to (2), relative to the condition of ultimate equilibrium, in the repulsive phase the energetic contribution due to the **internal energy E_{int}** is added. This energy generates the magnetic repulsive force due to the

overlapped equal poles, which now acts in the direction of separation of the charges. There will also be the electric attraction force between the charges and that due to any fluctuations. The internal energy E_{int} performs a work W_{rep} , which represents the displacement of the charges by the resulting repulsive force. The displacement of the charges involves a kinetic energy E_{kin} of the particles that become real. As a consequence of these considerations, the energy balance can be written as:

$$E_* + W_{\text{rep}} = 2 \frac{K_o Q_o^2}{c} * \omega_* + W_{* \text{virt}} + E_{\text{kin}} \quad (4)$$

where

E_* is the energy of the incident waves at the ultimate equilibrium condition, as in (2)

W_{rep} is the work due to the internal energy of repulsion. It is given by the resulting force of repulsion between the charges combined with the displacement that the force causes on the charges, which from virtual become real. If the separation between the particles occurs, kinetic energy E_{kin} and momentum occur, as in (4), otherwise it is recovered by the electrical and magnetic attractive forces to restore the initial condition when the wave leaves.

$\frac{K_o Q_o^2}{c} * \omega_*$ as in (3)

$W_{* \text{virt}}$ as in (2)

E_{kin} is the kinetic energy of the particles that from virtual become real, that is no longer bound in bosonic form.

Assuming that the total momentum of the system is retained, the minimum real momentum p_* of the individual real particles from the ultimate equilibrium also remains conditioned by the values of any energy fluctuations and the (indeterminable) actual charge distribution and relative masking during the Zitterbewegung phase. After separation, as verified in the laboratories, the mass of the single particle and its momentum have a value such as to ensure compliance with the special relativity according to the

$$E_*^2 = m^2 c^4 + p_*^2 c^2 \quad (5)$$

For values E_a of the incident waves greater than $E_* = 880 \text{ MeV}$ (ultimate equilibrium energy), therefore $E_a = E_* + \delta E > 880 \text{ MeV}$, the general energy balance can be described by

$$E_* + \delta E + W_{\text{rep}} = mc^2 + W_{* \text{virt}} + E_{\text{kin}} + \delta E_{\text{kin}} \quad (6)$$

where

δE_{kin} is the increase in kinetic energy due to δE .

For each particle is

$$E_a^2 = m^2 c^4 + p_a^2 c^2 \quad (7)$$

where $p_a = p_* + \Delta p$, in agreement with experimental data, is the momentum of the real particle (of its electric field) due to E_{int} and δE

$m = m_{e^+} = m_{e^-} = 0,511 \text{ MeV}$ is the mass of each particle according to the Standard Model, which can also be obtained through (3).

Results

Let us consider again the case of two incident waves with the ultimate equilibrium frequencies. For each virtual particle (5) can be developed as follows:

$$p_*^2 c^2 = h^2 \omega_*^2 - \frac{k_0^2 Q_0^4}{c^6} * \omega_*^2 * c^4, \text{ from which}$$

$$p_*^2 = \frac{\omega_*^2 h^2}{c^2} * \left[1 - \frac{k_0^2 Q_0^4}{h^2 c^2} \right] \text{ that we rewrite like this:}$$

$$p_* = \pm \sqrt{\frac{h^2}{\frac{c^2}{\omega_*^2}} * \left[1 - \frac{k_0^2 Q_0^4}{h^2 c^2} \right]} \quad (8)$$

$$\text{We impose (Ref.1)} \quad \frac{c^2}{\omega_*^2} = R_{\text{el}} \quad (9)$$

in which R_{el} is the radius of the electric field of the single virtual particle at the ultimate equilibrium condition. In this condition R_{el} coincides with the known radius of the electron's electric field (Ref.1). (9) can be generalized into

$$\frac{c^2}{\omega^2} = X \quad (10)$$

in which X represents the significant radial size that characterizes the charge distribution of the virtual boson. (8) can be therefore rewritten as:

$$p_* * R_{\text{el}} = \pm h \sqrt{1 - \frac{k_0^2 Q_0^4}{h^2 c^2}} \quad (11)$$

By defining the dimensionless quantity

$$\Delta = \sqrt{1 - \frac{k_0^2 Q_0^4}{h^2 c^2}} \quad (12)$$

(11) can be re written as

$$p_* R_{el} = \pm h \Delta \quad (13)$$

That we can generalized into

$$p_* X = \pm h \Delta \quad (14)$$

Imposing $R_{el} \neq 0$ we can divide within the root by R_{el}^4 as it follows

$$\Delta = \sqrt{1 - \frac{k_0^2 Q_0^4 / R_{el}^4}{h^2 c^2 / R_{el}^4}}$$

from $F_*^2 = k_0^2 Q_0^4 / R_{el}^4$, in which F_* is the electric force between the virtual charges at ultimate equilibrium (Ref.1), and from (9) we get

$$\Delta = \sqrt{1 - \frac{F_*^2}{\left(\frac{E_*}{R_{el}}\right)^2}} \quad (15)$$

writable also as

$$\Delta = \sqrt{1 - \frac{F_*^2 R_{el}^2}{E_*^2}} \quad (16)$$

From the consideration that R_{el} is also equal to the ultimate equilibrium distance (Ref.1), the amount $F_* R_{el}$ can be representative of the work done by the wave to separate the centers of the electric fields of the two virtual charges, from the initial null distance of total masking up to the distance of ultimate equilibrium. This distance, as written above, also coincides with the radius of the electric field of the particle (Ref.1).

We can therefore write $W_{*virt}^2 = F_*^2 R_{el}^2$, from which

$$\Delta = \sqrt{1 - \frac{L_{*virt}^2}{E_*^2}} \quad (17)$$

F_* , as explained above, remains indeterminable.

From (14) and (17) let us analyze four particular cases. The following conclusions, in compliance the initial hypotheses, are made possible thanks to (3) and present mathematical coherence with the considerations described by (2) and (4).

a) From (16), obtained however only in conditions of ultimate equilibrium, it can be noted that in the case in which the two virtual charges are in the conditions of the initial hypothesis of an unperturbed boson, which is truly unverifiable due to the background radiation (Ref.1), since the work of charges separation is zero, it is obtained

$$\Delta = 1 \quad (18)$$

Applying to (13) it follows

$$p * X = \pm h \quad (19)$$

The spin sign $s = \pm 1h$ is in agreement with the virtual bosons (i.a.) arrangement assumed at the beginning. In this condition the action possessed by the boson, quantifiable as h , is such that it manifests the momentum in the same way as a rotating charge distribution without translational components would do. The spatial magnitude X , under undisturbed condition, is represented by the significant radial size that characterizes the charge distribution of the virtual boson. According to Ref.1, under the conditions of stable, unperturbed equilibrium or even if the incident waves have low energies, the size X of the boson is much greater than R_{el} . For the unperturbed boson we therefore try to generalize as follows

$$p_0 * X_0 = \pm h \quad (20)$$

Rewritten in the other two conjugated variables, E =energy and t =time, (19) becomes

$$E * t = \pm h \quad (21)$$

which in conditions of stable, unperturbed equilibrium can be rewritten as

$$E_0 * t_0 = \pm h \quad (22).$$

For all bosonic virtual particles, respecting the value h of their spin, in the stable, unperturbed equilibrium state, the value of the quantities E, p, X, t of each virtual boson will tend to their respective equilibrium values E_0, p_0, X_0, t_0 that appears in (20) and (22).

b) With the mutual distancing between the two virtual charges due to the energy of the incident waves, defined unmasking, the action becomes partly rotary and

partly translational. When the incident energy is $E_* = W_{*virt} = F_* * R_{el}$, that is it is the exact quantity to produce work to reach the ultimate equilibrium, without further excess energy, in the position of ultimate equilibrium there is not the minimum energy value to produce the momentum necessary to separate the quantity of energy given by (3). In this case we obtain

$$\Delta = 0 \quad (23)$$

From (13) and by having imposed $R_{el} \neq 0$, consistently results $p_* = 0$.

As seen above, from this position, despite an insufficient energy value, if the repulsive force between the overlapping equal magnetic poles is triggered, the virtual particles could still separate and become real.

- c) Values $0 < \Delta < 1$ identify the virtual condition.
- d) When the particles separate from each other they will be subject to fermionic indeterminacy according to the known expression $\Delta p \Delta X \geq h$. Based on the described separation mechanism, the two real particles distance themselves along the spin axis due to the effect of the magnetic repulsion and possibly of the excess energy δE of the wave and/or fluctuations. Since they both have spins in the same direction, they will acquire helicity $+1/2$ and $-1/2$ respectively, in accordance with the properties of the particles described by the Standard Model. With the reduction of the volume of the pair-generating boson according to (19), the surrounding bosons, by transferring the energy of the wave that is abandoning them towards the generating boson, expand their volume, guaranteeing the system continuous and polarizable to the passage of the waves, as described in the initial hypotheses. In the condition in which the particles become real, the deformation of the surrounding bosons becomes permanent around the generated fermion, with curvature directed towards the center of the electric field of each fermion. This deformation, not the bosons, will follow the particle in its motion. The curvature of the bosons, in accordance with relativity, physically represents the mathematical curvature of the space-time, of such a magnitude as to give the mass effect equal to that attributed to the elementary particle, that is 0.511MeV. **The described phenomenon represents the birth of the gravitational field.** The energy and momentum values to refer to for experimental findings are the same as the many laboratory tests carried out over the years and preserved in the archives.

Conclusions

From the proposed considerations it follows that the model DESCRIPTIVE MATHEMATICAL MODEL FOR THE GENERATION OF PARTICLES AND ANTIPARTICLES IN A VACUUM: THE CASE OF THE ELECTRON AND THE POSITRON respects the conservation of energy and momentum in the description of the generation of pairs from the vacuum. The model starts from a plausible combination of virtual fermions with mutually null fields whose behavior is identical to that of the physical vacuum. It proposes a coherent physical interpretation of the phenomenon, offers a clear and intuitive explanation of the events observed and measured in the laboratories over the years.

Notes

A $Q_{e+}=1,6022E-19C$ and $Q_{e-}=-1,6022E-19C$ or, possibly, $Q_{e+}>1,6022E-19C$ and $|Q_{e-}|>1,6022E-19C$, but not less than these values

B According with the general relativity, this value of the mass corresponds to an energy value given by $E=mc^2$

C We can calculate the size of the electric field of the real particle, but not the size of the actual real particle. The real particle, compared with the i.a.'s single electric charge, is a concentrated electric charge, which could also be different orders of magnitude smaller than the size of the respective electric fields